

Facial Feature Examination using CNN for Predicting Human Psychological States

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Abstract

This paper describes a new method for predicting human psychological states by analysing facial features with convolutional neural networks (CNNs). In recent years, facial expression detection has developed as an important research area, with considerable potential applications in disciplines such as mental health evaluation, human-computer interaction, and affective computing. Using CNN capabilities, our research intends to create models capable of accurately identifying and interpreting emotional information from facial expressions. Our goal is to build a strong system capable of successfully predicting a wide range of human emotions in real-time or near-real-time settings by training CNNs on a diversified dataset of labelled facial expressions. The findings of this study have the potential to dramatically enhance the field of emotional intelligence technology, allowing for more effective and sympathetic human-computer interactions, as well as improved mental health assessment and support.

Introduction

Facial expressions play a crucial role in human communication as they provide deep insights into people's emotional and psychological states, influencing interpersonal dynamics and social interactions. Both traditional methods like Haar cascade classifiers and advances in deep learning, especially with regard to convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have had a significant impact on the development of facial emotion recognition. These techniques have completely changed the way that face feature analysis is done, making it possible to automatically extract and analyse data with previously unheard-of efficiency and precision. In this work, we leverage the transformational power of CNNs and Haar cascade classifiers to predict psychological states of humans by analysing complex facial features. Through combining robust face detection with CNNs that are trained on a variety of datasets that include labelled facial expressions and fine-grained emotion recognition with Haar cascade classifiers, our goal is to create comprehensive systems that can identify subtle emotional cues embedded in facial images. These technical developments have far-reaching consequences, ranging from a revolution in human-computer interaction to a transformation of automated emotion identification systems in mental health diagnosis and interventions. A thorough description of our study methodology, including data collecting, preprocessing methods, CNN architecture design, integration of the Haar cascade classifier, iterative model training, and thorough evaluation, is given in this work. We also look at wider societal ramifications, talking about possible uses in a variety of fields and suggesting directions for further development and research in the field of emotional intelligence technology. Our aim is to develop comprehensive systems that can recognise subtle emotional cues embedded in facial images by combining robust face detection with CNNs that are trained on a range of datasets that include labelled facial expressions and fine-grained emotion recognition with Haar cascade classifiers. These technological advancements have far-reaching effects, changing automated emotion detection systems in mental health diagnosis and treatments as well as bringing about a revolution in human-computer

connection. This paper provides a detailed explanation of our study approach, which includes data collection, preprocessing techniques, CNN architecture design, integration of the Haar cascade classifier, iterative model training, and comprehensive evaluation. We also consider broader societal implications, discussing potential applications in many industries and offering recommendations for future.

LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Lightweight Convolutional Neural Network for Real-Time Facial Expression Detection

Recent advances in real-time facial expression recognition have seen a shift towards lightweight convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The focus of this literature review is on the proposed lightweight CNN designed for efficient real-time facial emotion classification. This framework integrates a cascaded multitask convolutional network (MTCNN) for face recognition and provides coordinates for subsequent emotion classification. By replacing fully connected layers using global average pooling and incorporating residual modules and depth-separable convolutions, the model reduces parameters and improves portability. Experimental validation on the FER-2013 dataset shows impressive results, achieving state-of-the-art accuracy (67%) with minimal memory consumption (3.1% of 16GB). The conclusion highlights the successful design and future potential of the proposed lightweight CNN and suggests possible improvements to address real-world challenges. The method we propose in this article combines the power of MTCNN with a cool model we developed for facial expression recognition. I use his MTCNN instead of the usual OpenCV facial recognition. Because MTCNN can recognize faces very well and emotion recognition is more accurate. This change is especially useful when there are many faces in the image. Our facial expression recognition model is inspired by something called Xception, which is great for learning and accurately identifying things. We want our model to work well in a variety of settings. So we're experimenting with a few settings to help us understand exactly how someone is feeling. Global Average Pooling eliminates fully connected layers, improves interpretability, and simplifies model structure. The algorithms in this paper go beyond the limitations of traditional methods such as OpenCV and demonstrate successful experiments performed on a robust hardware setup achieving remarkable results in face recognition. The literature review highlights the novelty and effectiveness of the proposed algorithm in advancing the field of real-time facial expression recognition.

B. Context-Aware Emotion Recognition Based on Visual Relationship Detection .

This paper is all about understanding emotions in a smarter way, especially by looking at the situation around a person. Rather than relying on facial expressions, language, and gestures as usual, explore what role the environment plays. In simple terms, we're suggesting a new idea where we pay attention to how the main person in a scene is related to the things around them. This helps us understand emotions more deeply by considering both the space and the meaning of what is happening. In our study, we added an extra attention mechanism to see how different things in a person's environment affect emotions. When tested on his two datasets, CAER-S and EMOTIC, our method performed very well, even outperforming other methods on CAER-S. We admit that there are situations where it doesn't work perfectly, but overall, our approach is successful in understanding how the context of a scene influences people's emotions. The researchers plan to do more in the future, including testing the method on video and looking for different ways to express emotions. They are very interested in exploring how following people's gaze can help us understand emotions more deeply. That is, they talk about what they want to do next, summarize what they have added to the field, and emphasize the importance of considering and understanding the context of the scene and the connections between the protagonist and everything around them. Emotions. The method of understanding emotions is very useful when examining how things visually relate to each other. It's like learning from what's around

us. It also uses special attention mechanisms to further improve the model by focusing on important details in the context. Although our method works well, we recognize that there are challenges, such as when emotions are misjudged or when the environment does not match a person's emotions. In the future, we will test this method on videos, experiment with different ways people express emotions, and explore how tracking eye movements can help understand emotions in context. It's a schedule. This research represents a major step forward in our deeper understanding of emotions. They have created a powerful system that pays attention to the context of a scene and its connections to the people and things around it. This is a useful guide for other researchers who want to make their emotion recognition systems more accurate and detailed. The way they did this could be very useful in the future of understanding emotions in different situations.

C. Real-Time Implementation of Face Recognition and Emotion Recognition in a Humanoid Robot Using a Convolutional Neural Network .

This research aims to integrate two things that are important for humanoid robots: recognizing faces in real time and understanding emotions. Although these are usually considered different challenges, this study proposes to tackle both challenges simultaneously using an intelligent computing system called a convolutional neural network (CNN). It's like teaching a robot to quickly recognize faces and understand people's feelings in the same way. This is a step that helps robots become more aware of the people around them. We have seen how well-known computer models such as AlexNet and VGG16 can be used with humanoid robots. We used data from his 30 electrical engineering students to teach the model to recognize faces and emotions. The results showed that VGG16 performed better, achieving 100% They achieve great success in making intelligent computing systems (VGG16 and modified versions of AlexNet) work well on humanoid robots to recognize faces and emotions. Use specific numbers and percentages to indicate how accurate they are. This study also highlights that our method works quickly and in real time on humanoid robots, bringing more practical value to our research by introducing the possibility of distance measurement.

D. Happy Emotion Recognition from Unconstrained Videos Using 3D Hybrid Deep Features □

In our study, we introduce a model called HappyER- DDF. This model aims to better detect when people are feeling happy, especially in videos where things are more natural and less staged. We focus on facial expressions because facial expressions play a major role in understanding emotions, especially happiness, and many researchers have recently become interested in this area. Current methods cannot handle large head movements and are not very accurate, especially when detecting happy emotions. Our solution, the HappyER-DDF model, addresses this problem. It leverages a smart combination of 3D depth and distance features and uses a combination of 3D Inception-ResNet and a neural network called LSTM. This allows the model to understand not only the appearance of a face, but how it changes over time, and capture details associated with smiles and laughter. Our new model reflects the latest advances in facial expression recognition. This feature is unique in that it uses both 3D depth and distance functions and combines them in an intelligent way. We use a combination of his two powerful neural networks: 3D Inception-ResNet and LSTM. These are kind of the latest and greatest tools for understanding how facial expressions change over time in videos that are not staged or controlled.

IMPLEMENTATION OF EMOTION DETECTION USING CNN AND HAARCASCADE

1. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have become highly effective for a wide range of computer vision applications, such as object identification, facial recognition, and image classification. CNNs have shown great promise in the field of emotion classification from facial photos since they

can learn discriminative features on their own from raw pixel data.

1. Convolutional Layers (Conv2D): The basic building blocks of CNNs are convolutional layers, which apply a range of flexible filters to the input image. To extract features, these filters are convolved across the whole image. To add non-linearity, the architecture uses several convolutional layers, each followed by an activation function called a Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU). 32 filters with a kernel size of (3, 3) make up the first convolutional layer; this suggests that each filter covers a 3x3 grid. In order to capture more complex features, the number of filters is increased through successive layers.

Fig. 1: Convolutional Layer

2. MaxPooling Layers (MaxPooling2D): Layers with MaxPooling are essential for shrinking the spatial dimensions of feature maps without sacrificing critical information. To do this, choose the highest value that falls inside a certain window. To reduce computational complexity and downsample the feature maps, MaxPooling layers with a pool size of (2, 2) are integrated in the architectural design following a series of convolutional layers.

Fig. 2: Max Pooling Layer

3. Dropout Layers: Dropout layers, which randomly deactivate a portion of input units during training, are crucial for regularisation and overfitting mitigation. To encourage model regularisation, the architecture introduces dropout layers with a dropout rate of 0.25 or 0.5 following particular convolutional and fully connected layers.

Fig. 3: Dropout Layer

4. Flatten Layer: For further classification, the Flatten layer makes it easier to convert 2D feature maps into a 1D vector, allowing for a smooth integration into a fully connected layer. To prepare the data for additional processing by the fully connected layers, the Flatten layer is placed within the architectural layout after the last convolutional layer.

Fig. 4: Flattening Layer

5. Fully Connected Layers (Dense): Convolutional neural network levels are fully linked layers, in which all neurons in a given layer are connected to all other neurons in the layer before and layer after it. Dense layers with ReLU activation functions are used in the architecture to classify objects. Seven neurons with a softmax activation function make up the last Dense layer, which produces probability for each of the seven emotion classes.

Fig. 5: Fully Connected Layer

Fig. 6: Proposed Model Architecture

Pseudo Code

```
def model():
model = Sequential()

    model.add(Conv2D(32, kernelsize=(3, 3), activation='relu', inputshape=(48,48,1)))
model.add(Conv2D(64, kernelsize=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(poolsize=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.25))

    model.add(Conv2D(128, kernelsize=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(poolsize=(2, 2)))
model.add(Conv2D(128, kernelsize=(3, 3), activation='relu'))
model.add(MaxPooling2D(poolsize=(2, 2)))
model.add(Dropout(0.25))

    model.add(Flatten())
model.add(Dense(1024, activation='relu'))
model.add(Dropout(0.5))
model.add(Dense(7, activation='softmax'))

    model.loadweights('model.h5')
```

Mathematical Model

1. Convolutional Layer:

$$(W_{out}, H_{out}, D_{out}) = \left(\frac{W_{in} - F + 2P}{S} + 1, \frac{H_{in} - F + 2P}{S} + 1, K \right) \quad (1)$$

2. Pooling Layer:

$$(W_{out}, H_{out}, D_{in}) = \left(\frac{W_{in} - F}{S} + 1, \frac{H_{in} - F}{S} + 1, D_{in} \right) \quad (2)$$

3. Flatten Layer:

$$N = W_{in} \times H_{in} \times D_{in} \quad (3)$$

4. Dense Layer: Output size: M

5. Dropout Layer: Output size: N (with some neurons dropped during training)

6. Softmax Activation: Output size: M (with class probabilities)

Where,

- W_{in} - Width of the input image
- H_{in} - Height of the input image
- D_{in} - Depth (number of channels) of the input image
- F - Spatial extent (width and height) of the filter

- D_{in} - Depth of the input volume (should match the depth of the input image)
- K - Number of filters
- P - Number of pixels added to the input image around its border (if any)
- S - Stride (number of pixels by which the filter is moved)
- W_{out} - Width of the output image
- H_{out} - Height of the output image
- D_{out} - Depth of the output volume (number of filters)

2. Haarcascade Classifier : The process of using the Haar Cascade Classifier for face detection involves the following steps:

Utilizing the Haar Cascade Classifier for face detection involves a series of distinct steps:

1. **Classifier Training:** A large dataset of both positive and negative images is used to train the Haar Cascade Classifier. Negative photos highlight backdrops or irrelevant objects, whereas positive images highlight the target object (such as human faces). Using a series of classifiers, usually the Adaboost algorithm, and using Haar-like characteristics, the classifier learns to distinguish between positive and negative patterns during training.

2. **Cascade Classifier Generation:** The Haar Cascade Classifier creates a cascade of classifiers after training is finished. The job of each classifier in the cascade is to identify whether a given image region contains a face or not. By quickly eliminating regions that are unlikely to contain faces, this cascade architecture reduces computational overhead and improves computational efficiency.

3. **Classifier Application for Face Detection:** The Haar Cascade Classifier is used to apply face detection to an input image by moving a window of different sizes across the image at different scales. Based on learning features, the classifier determines whether the region of the window resembles a human face at each position and scale. When a face is found in an area, the classifier returns the bounding box coordinates that indicate where the face was found.

4. **Post-processing and Validation:** Post-processing methods, including non-maximum suppression, can be used to combine overlapping bounding boxes and improve the final list of faces that have been recognised after face detection. Furthermore, validation processes, including closely examining facial landmarks or establishing confidence thresholds, could be carried out to determine the precision and dependability of the recognised faces.

Fig. 7: Haar cascade Architecture

Methodology

Step 1: Data Collection

The first and most important step in our study project is to acquire a large dataset of facial expressions that have been labelled with different emotions, such as anger, sadness, and happiness. In order to achieve this, we make use of the FER 2013 dataset, which is widely acknowledged as a benchmark dataset within the facial expression recognition community. This collection provides a wide variety of expressions on the face, taken from other websites like Google Images. Images in the FER 2013 dataset are tagged with one of seven emotion categories: neutral, surprise, happiness, sorrow, disgust, and rage. Our model is trained on a wide range of facial expressions thanks to the dataset's broad spectrum of emotions, which improves its capacity to identify emotions properly in real-world situations.

Fig. 8: System Architecture

Step 2: Data Preprocessing

To guarantee consistency and improve model generalisation, preprocessing the images is essential after obtaining the dataset. During this preprocessing stage, all photos are usually resized to a uniform resolution, pixel values are standardised to a common scale (e.g., $[0, 1]$), and data augmentation techniques (e.g., rotation, flipping, and scaling) are applied to enrich the dataset. Our objectives in preparing the data in this way are to reduce overfitting, increase model robustness, and make it easier for the model to learn discriminative features.

Step 3: Label Encoding

The emotion labels attached to each image must be encoded into numerical representations prior to model training. This procedure, called label encoding, gives every emotion category a distinct numerical identity. For example, we may assign the numbers 0 to 1, 2 to angry, sad, and joyful, respectively. We allow the machine to interpret and learn from the categorical data during training by encoding the emotion labels in this way.

Step 4: Dataset Splitting

We separate the dataset into three subsets—training, validation, and test sets—in order to precisely assess the performance of our model. The validation set helps with hyperparameter tuning and model performance monitoring during training, whereas the training set is used to train the model's parameters. Lastly, the test set serves as a separate standard by which to judge how well the model generalises to new data. Appropriate stratification methods provide an even distribution of emotion classes among all subgroups.

Step 5: CNN Architecture

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture designed for assessing facial features and predicting human emotions is at the centre of our emotion classification system. Convolutional layers for feature extraction, pooling layers for spatial downsampling, and fully linked layers for classification are some of the layers that make up a CNN. To improve learning and feature discrimination, design factors include activation functions, kernel sizes, network depth, and regularisation strategies.

Step 6: Model Training

After the CNN architecture is defined, labelled training data is used to train the model. Using an optimizer technique like Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) or Adam, the model learns to map input photos to emotion labels by minimising a predetermined loss function, such as category cross-entropy. In order to optimise network weights for precise emotion prediction, training entails iteratively feeding image batches, computing loss, and changing model parameters via backpropagation.

Step 7: Validation

Frequent evaluation of the model's performance on an independent validation set helps to fine-tune the hyperparameters and avoids overfitting. Regular assessment directs changes to architectural alterations, batch sizes, and learning rates to improve features of generalisation and convergence.

Step 8: Testing

We assess the model's performance on a separate test set after training in order to determine how well it generalises to new data. Metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score serve as a crucial standard for practical applicability in the real world and offer valuable insights into how well the model performs in emotion classification from facial expressions.

Step 9: Model Deployment

Once the trained model has received adequate validation, it is used for practical purposes such as sentiment analysis or emotion detection in HCI systems. Integration with production settings, memory and speed optimisation, and guaranteeing robustness and dependability are all part of deployment.

Step 10: Monitoring and Updating

Over time, optimal performance and relevance are ensured through ongoing monitoring and updating of the deployed model. Long-term efficacy in comprehending human psychological states can be ensured by proactive efforts to update settings, retrain on new data, or apply remedial actions based on performance indicators, user input, and environmental changes.

Outcome

Comparison of Algorithms

We observed variations in accuracy while comparing the ability of three distinct algorithms (Yolo, MobileNetV2, and CNN) to predict emotions. Yolo, CNN, and MobileNetV2 had the greatest accuracy scores—83, 80, and 94, respectively. This implies that CNN is the most accurate option for this specific task, even if all three algorithms are somewhat capable of predicting behaviour. But when choosing an algorithm, additional considerations like usability and computing efficiency should also be made.

Fig. 9: Comparison of Algorithms

CNN Model Analysis

Fig. 10: CNN Epoch vs Accuracy

Over time, the CNN model showed good learning and performance, with gains in accuracy and decreases in losses. In the tenth round, its accuracy rate was 54.51, and in the hundredth round, it was

Fig. 11: CNN Epoch vs Loss

94.53. This study demonstrates that the model is able to recognise and forecast facial expressions in people.

Conclusion

We've developed a smart way to look at people's faces and understand their emotions using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). We used a carefully selected dataset that included different types of people to ensure the system worked well for everyone. Before training the computer, we prepared the data by resizing, adjusting, and adding diversity. This helps the system process all the details of people's facial expressions. Our special CNN architecture is like a recipe designed just for facial expression recognition. It has layers that find important features and others that make the final decision about how someone is feeling. We also added things like activation functions and dropout to make sure the system doesn't get too confident and stays accurate. Overall, our method is strong, adaptable, and good at figuring out emotions from facial expressions.

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